

Syntheses of 2-Substituted-1,2-dihydro-1-oxo-4-isoquinoline-carboxamides and 4-Amidoximino-2-substituted-1,2-dihydro-1-oxoisoquinolines as Antimicrobial Agents

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Various substituted-1-oxoisoquinolines were prepared starting with homophthalic anhydride. The intermediate aminomethylene homophthalic anhydride yields 1-oxoisoquinoline acids and amides in presence of 10% solution of sodium hydroxide and secondary amine respectively. The substituted-1-oxoisoquinoline acids were then converted to substituted amidoximino-1-oxoisoquinolines and their antimicrobial activity was determined.

A review of literature reports diverse biological activities¹ for 1-oxoisoquinolines. In view of this, various 4-substituted-1-oxoisoquinolines were synthesised and their antimicrobial activity was studied. Homophthalic anhydride is reported² to react with amines in presence of triethyl orthoformate to give aminomethylenehomophthalic anhydride (2). When heated with equimolar amount of pyrrolidine in xylene, 2a gave 3Aa in good yield (Scheme 1). The mass spectrum (M^+ at m/z 332) and the elemental analysis gave molecular formula $C_{21}H_{20}N_2O_2$. Its ir spectrum (nujol) displayed peaks at 1670 ($=C-CO-N$) and 1630 cm^{-1} ($CO-N$). The pmr spectrum ($CDCl_3$) exhibited signals at δ 1.7–2.0 (4H, m, $2 \times \beta-CH_2$ of pyrrolidine), 2.4 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.2 and 3.7 (2H, bs each, $2 \times N-CH_2$), 7.1–8.0 (8H, m, ArH and $N-CH=C$) and 8.4–8.6 (1H, m, C_3-H), thus confirming the assigned structure of 2-(4-methylphenyl)-4-N-pyrrolidinocarbonyl-1,2-dihydro-1-oxoisoquinoline (3Aa).

Various compounds having amidoximino substituents are reported to possess biological activities³. Hence, it was thought interesting to introduce amidoximino group in the 1(2H)-oxoisoquinoline skeleton and study their antimicrobial activity.

The intermediate aminomethylenehomophthalic anhydride is reported² to rearrange in presence of HCl to give 2-substituted-1-oxo-4-isoquinoline carboxylic acid (4). We found that the acids (4) are also obtained in good yields in 10% sodium hydroxide solution from the aminomethylenehomophthalic anhydride. The substituted-isoquinoline carboxylic acids were converted by conventional routes to isoquinoline carboxamides, and then to isoquinoline carbonitrile (6). Compounds 6 on treatment with hydroxylaminehydrochloride yields substituted-

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) RNH_2 , $HC(OC_2H_5)_3$; (ii) R^1R^2NH , (iii) 10% Aq. NaOH, (iv) $SOCl_2$, (v) NH_3 , (vi) $NH_2OH \cdot HCl$, Py, Na_2CO_3

R	NR^1R^2
a; 4-Methylphenyl	A; Pyrrolidino
b; 4-(α, α -Trifluoromethyl)phenyl	B; Piperidino
c; 4-Chlorophenyl	C; Morpholino
d; 3-Nitrophenyl	
e; 2-(5-Mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl)	
f; 4-Methoxyphenyl	
g; 2-(4,6-Dimethylpyrimidinyl)	
h; 4-(N,N-Dimethylamino)phenyl	

amidoximinoisoquinoline derivatives (7). The mass spectrum (M^+ at m/z 293) and the elemental analysis

gave molecular formula $C_{17}H_{15}N_3O_2$ for **7a**. Its ir spectrum (nujol) showed bands at 1 660 (C=O), 3 350 (NH₂) and 3 410 cm^{-1} (OH). The pmr spectrum (DMSO-*d*₆+TFA) exhibited signals at δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.1 (2H, s, NH₂, D₂O exchangeable), 5.6 (1H, s, OH, D₂O exchangeable), 7.2–7.9 (8H, m, ArH and N-CH=C), 8.4–8.6 (1H, m, C₈-H), thus confirming the assigned structure of 4-amidoximino-2-(4-methyl)phenyl-1,2-dihydro-1-oxoisoquinoline.

Biological activity: Compounds **3**, **4** and **7** were evaluated for their antibacterial activity by ditch-plate technique⁴ using concentration levels of 10 and 20 mg ml⁻¹. The test organisms employed were gram-positive bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram-negative bacteria *Salmonella typhosa*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Pseudomonas pyocyanae* and *Proteus vulgaris*. The compounds **4a–f** and **7a–f** were found to inhibit all the organism tested at the concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. The compounds **3Aa–3Ch** showed promising activity against *P. pyocyanae* and inhibited *S. aureus*, *S. typhosa*, *S. dysenteriae* and *P. vulgaris* at 20 mg ml⁻¹.

Experimental

All the melting points reported are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 681 spectrometer, pmr spectra on Hitachi R-600 and JEOL FX-90Q spectrometers and mass spectra on a Shimadzu QP-1000 spectrometer.

General procedure for synthesis of 2a–h: Homophthalic anhydride (10 mmol) and amine (10 mmol) were refluxed in triethylorthoformate (7 ml) for 15 min. Ethanol was then added to it and the resulting was dried and crystallised from DMF.

General procedure for the synthesis of 3Aa–3Ch: Substituted-aminomethylhomophthalic anhydride (**2**; 10 mmol) was refluxed with secondary amine (10 mmol) in xylene (5 ml) for 3 h. The reaction mixture on standing yielded white solid which dried and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (80 : 20).

General procedure for the synthesis of 4a–f: Substituted-aminomethylhomophthalic anhydride (**1**; 10 mmol) was heated on a steam-bath with ethanolic 10% solution of sodium hydroxide till the solution became clear. On acidification it yielded a white solid which was dried and crystallised from acetic acid.

General procedure for synthesis of 5a–f: Compound **4** (10 mmol) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (10 ml) for 2 h. The excess thionyl chloride was then distilled off and the resulting clear solution of acid chloride was then poured into cold liquor ammonia with stirring. The separated solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

General procedure for synthesis of 6a–f: Compound **5** (10 mmol) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (10 ml) for 2 h. The excess of thionyl

chloride was then distilled off and the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water with stirring. The separated solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

General procedure for synthesis of 7a–f: A mixture of **6** (2.5 mmol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (2.5 mmol), sodium carbonate (1.6 g), pyridine (15 ml) and ethanol (5 ml) was heated at 100° for 5 h and then filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and the solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol.

The physical data of the compounds prepared are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd no	M p °C	Yield %	Mol formula/ (Mol wt)
2a	256	90	$C_{17}H_{13}NO_3$ (279)
2b	240	88	$C_{17}H_{10}F_3NO_3$ (333)
2c	262 ^a	91	$C_{16}H_{10}ClNO_3$ (299 5)
2d	255	88	$C_{16}H_{10}N_2O_5$ (310)
2e	232 ^d	89	$C_{12}H_7N_3O_3S_2$ (305)
2f	232	90	$C_{17}H_{12}NO_4$ (295)
2g	264	87	$C_{16}H_{13}N_2O_3$ (295)
2h	252	89	$C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_3$ (308)
3Aa	219	72	$C_{21}H_{10}N_2O_2$ (332)
3Ab	163	76	$C_{21}H_{17}F_3N_2O_2$ (386)
3Ac	162	71	$C_{20}H_{17}ClN_2O_2$ (352 5)
3Ad	123	56	$C_{10}H_{17}N_3O_4$ (363)
3Ae	270 ^b	69	$C_{16}H_{14}N_4S_2O_2$ (358)
3Af	221	69	$C_{21}H_{20}N_2O_3$ (348)
3Ag	165	53	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_2$ (348)
3Ah	187	81	$C_{22}H_{13}N_3O_2$ (361)
3Ba	195	62	$C_{22}H_{22}N_2O_2$ (346)
3Bb	147	71	$C_{22}H_{16}N_3N_2O_2$ (400)
3Bc	242	69	$C_{21}H_{15}ClN_2O_2$ (366 5)
3Bd	174	63	$C_{21}H_{16}N_3O_4$ (377)
3Be	280 ^b	68	$C_{17}H_{16}N_4O_2S_2$ (372)
3Bf	135	65	$C_{22}H_{22}N_2O_3$ (362)
3Bg	181	67	$C_{21}H_{22}N_4O_2$ (362)
3Bh	120	57	$C_{23}H_{24}N_3O_2$ (375)
3Ca	180	71	$C_{21}H_{20}N_4O_3$ (348)
3Cb	208	75	$C_{21}H_{17}F_3N_2O_3$ (402)
3Cc	184	81	$C_{20}H_{17}ClN_2O_3$ (368 5)

(Table 1 contd.)

3Cd	132	57	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ (379)
3Ce	165 ^b	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂ (374)
3Cf	176	65	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ (364)
3Cg	172	61	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ (364)
3Ch	137	56	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃ (377)
4a	298	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO ₃ (279)
4b	210	82	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ F ₃ NO ₃ (333)
4c	270 ^a	64	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClNO ₃ (299.5)
4d	275d	73	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₅ (310)
4e	247	61	C ₁₉ H ₇ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂ (305)
4f	245	73	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO ₄ (295)
4g	175	62	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ (295)
5a	235	91	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ (278)
5b	185	97	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ F ₃ N ₂ O ₂ (332)
5c	182	89	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ (298.5)
5d	201	92	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ (309)
5e	220d	91	C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ (304)
5f	204	96	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ (294)
5g	160	92	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ (294)
6a	181	92	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ O (260)
6b	148	96	C ₁₇ H ₉ F ₃ N ₂ O (314)
6c	170	89	C ₁₆ H ₉ ClN ₂ O (280.5)

6d	195	91
6e	182	91
6f	108	92
6g	120	92
7a	252	61
7b	227	52
7c	182	67
7d	205	51
7e	211	52
7f	140	59
7g	181	51

(Table 1 contd.)

C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₃ O ₄ (291)
C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₄ OS ₂ (286)
C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ (276)
C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O (276)
C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ (293)
C ₁₇ H ₁₂ F ₃ N ₂ O ₂ (347)
C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ (313.5)
C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₄ (324)
C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂ (320)
C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₃ (309)
C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ (309)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses
 **^aLit. m.p Ref. 2; ^bCrystallised from MeOH-H₂O.

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